

Opinions of Teachers Regarding the Administrative Authority and Student-Teacher Ratio: Parameters that Affect Quality Education in Public Sector at Secondary Schools

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 12, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 30, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Administrative Authority, Student-Teacher Ratio, Parameters, Quality, Education, Secondary Schools</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5741122</p>	<p><i>The purpose of the study was to examine the administrative authority and student-teacher ratio as parameters that affect quality education in public sector at secondary schools. The focus of the study was to examine the parameters that affect quality education in terms of principals' administrative authority and student-teacher ratio in the public sector secondary schools. The population of the study comprised of teachers of 96 public secondary schools of districts Mardan and Swabi. Through random sampling technique, 10 teachers from each of the 96 schools were included in the sample hence the sample consisted of 960 teachers. The data was collected from the respondents through questionnaires. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques such as frequency, Percentage and ANOVA by using SPSS. The findings of the study revealed that the teachers prefer corporal punishment for their students, teachers preferred to maintain the discipline of the students, teachers cared about the uniform of the students and teachers help the slow learner in academic affairs which are the significant parameters of quality education. Students obey teachers' orders in school matters, teachers help in solving administrative problems for the principals, there is a cordial relationship between the principal and teachers and there is a cordial relationship between teachers and students which are significant parameters of quality education. The standard class size (30-35), the number of science teachers in school, the number of arts teachers in school, the overall number of teachers in school, and the students- teachers ratio in school are the significant parameters of quality education.</i></p>

Introduction

Quality education is concerned with early childhood improvement, regular presence for learning, support of family, and public contribution. The provision of facilities at school, the infrastructure of the school, provision of dispensary, class size, conducive environment, teachers' skill, teachers' professional development and performance, discipline to attain expected results. However, the peacefulness, student-teacher ratio, consistent curriculum, accomplishments in knowledge and facility, unending support for student-centered knowledge, financial support, the methodology of teachers, administrative support, management, and leadership, using developmental assessment, outcomes required by parents and public, practical approaches are also attaining expected results (UNICEF, 2000).

It has turned out to be essential to look for choices to move the effectiveness of general secondary schools to the most standard with the goal that students would benefit from assistance to accomplish their objectives. In each school, the wish of the students is to reach a higher level of achievement and schools have powerful urges for all students to succeed. Recently, the people has achieved a high level of improvement as far as access is concerned. Thus, the time has come to concentrate on the attributes of quality. According to the Ministry of Education (2008), for Ethiopian education, the vital concentration must be quality of education. Then again, in the majority of schools at the secondary level, the issue of an excellent education is considered as the duty of the government alone. However, the reality is that it is the whole school-community concern that needs the involvement of all available human resources.

In Pakistan the education system is divided generally into six levels: Playgroup (for the age from 3 to 5 years), Primary level (from grade one through five), Middle schools (grades six through eight), High schools (grades nine and ten, leading to the Secondary School Certificate or SSC), Intermediate schools (grades eleven and twelve, leading to a Higher Secondary School Certificate or HSSC), and University level programs leading to undergraduate and graduate degrees (Education system in Pakistan, 2018). The Provincial and Federal government granted the funds to the public or government schools while private schools are funded fully or partly by students' tuition fees and administered by a private body. Private schools are free to a large extent

from the interference of the government funds (Wang, 2013). As in Pakistan, the standard of learning is declining in public sectors, so it appears appropriate to study the standard of schooling. So it may be studying the parameters that affect the quality of education in the public sector at the secondary level in Mardan division. This study was conducted to investigate the parameters affecting quality education in terms of principals' administrative authority in public sector secondary schools and; to investigate the parameters affecting quality education in terms of student-teacher ratio in public sector secondary schools. Following research questions were also developed to seek their satisfactory answers. Is there any significant difference in the quality of principals' administrative authority that affects the quality of education in the public sector at secondary schools? Is there any significant difference in the quality of the student-teacher ratio that affects the quality of education in the public sector at secondary schools?

Literature Review

Quality parameters are "standard reports made in such a way that they ensure complete study of the most relevant fields of the quality education" (National Assessment and Accreditation Council, 2007). According to Kathleen (2003), principals are leaders having visions and expertise in goal setting and are in a position to monitor, analyze and offer feedback both to teachers and students. The demand for quality, directly interconnected to the quality of administration and management of principals, financial powers, teachers' qualification, professional development, infrastructure, and an environment, provided to them by the educational institutions. The level of capability of teachers, curricula, and the standard of student performance is the major contributor in aspects that determine the quality of education. Jacobson (2011) conducted a study in England and he found that the effects of school and leadership are shown to influence changes in academic achievement through their effects on teachers as well as on teaching quality. The study shows, in particular, the significance of a model of leadership practice that produces a systematic and positive behavioral climate, encouraging learner motivation and a learning culture that predicts positive changes in the behavior of students and attendance as intermediate outcomes that themselves cause improvement in the attainment of objectives. Rather than stressing on the process of education in terms of quality of education, the central focus is now shifted to improvements as to whether student results can be improved through leadership. In simple words, although the quality of teachers has a substantial influence on the motivation and achievement of students, leadership has a great influence over teachers that plays a major role in their motivation. Also, Fullan (2001) claims that leadership's quality is crucial in determining the teachers' motivation and the quality of their teaching, which in turn affects the performance of the students.

In a school set up, what is extremely expected of school leadership or the leader's output or outcome? The traditional view of leadership was to consider it non-systemic and individualistic perspective. The contemporary view, on the other hand, views educational leadership as a systemic force, which empowers as well as transforms collective learning and is community-oriented. Gronn (2004) and Spillance (2007) are of the view that school leadership today does not mean formally designated positions only; rather it has become a collective construct that is to be distributed among teachers and assists staff for purposes of inculcating better working relationships plus networks. The researcher agrees that making a broader viewpoint on leadership where everyone shows responsibility makes not only the handing over of duties easier but also somewhat less difficult and less demanding for teachers as well as supporting staff. To say it in other words, making such an environment gives support to innovation. Silns and Mulford (2002) contend that if schools are to become better at enhancing pupil learning, they should produce multiple opportunities for teachers to improve, innovate, and learn. To put it another way, The outcomes of students are more likely to become better when leadership is distributed across the school and its community; when teachers are given powers and their self-esteem and importance are recognized and elevated (Crowther, 2000).

However, this does not appear to be the situation in practice, Southworth (2003), conducted a study and confirms that generally the urgent tasks are given priority over important tasks. This is the reason that so many principals are of the view that they spend enough time on administration-related tasks, the tasks related to budget, and copious other school problems and hence cannot do sufficient work with the teachers on instruction-related issues. He further says that the principals often complain that they do not have sufficient time to become the "instructional leaders" they think they are supposed to be. It was concluded in the study that to cope with the constraints that are imposed by time, it is indispensable for effective leaders to pay proper heed to build their teachers' capacity by the use of staff development. The encouraging conditions where they can get themselves engaged in collective explorations of their varied experiences as well as approaches to teaching and learning. The researcher got full awareness of the various constraints that hinder capacity building in a school. This is the responsibility of the school leader to foster trust, competency, a mutual spirit, attitude, and the spirit of teamwork. When a school culture is established and collaboration is created, the expertise and skills of every staff member will come up with a positive change and commitment.

Student-Teacher Ratio: the student-teacher ratio should be taken in balance and the classrooms should be designed keeping in mind efficient interaction and communication. Students ought to have the capability to

effectively observe and hear the teacher and also other students. Berry's study (2002) on the level of classroom noise found that disorder levels in the classroom should not surpass 68db or about 68-69 lb (noise or disorder levels). As stated, if the size of the classroom is not according to the standard measure, so the students will not be able to understand what is being taught to them and will get distracted because of the noise in the adjacent classrooms. Therefore, for better quality, the physical learning environment of the class should be as mentioned above and if there is no balance in the ratio of students-teachers, then it affects the quality of education.

Berry states that the classroom is the most crucial area of a school where teachers and students go to spend most of their time and the learning process takes place there. He talked about the conditions that need improvement to make it a better place as learning occurs there. He stressed that the classroom should be constructed in such a way that can accommodate the students with sufficient space and that the strength of the students does not surpass thirty-five. He also mentioned that in each school the teachers should be appointed based on the student ratio. The lower number of children per classroom and as well as in the schools will enhance teacher-pupil communication and interaction. Thus, the classrooms must be constructed with effective interaction and communication in mind. The students ought to effortlessly observe and hear the teachers and their class fellows (Berry, 2002).

Research Methodology

The major purpose of the study was to find the parameters affecting quality education in public sector secondary schools. For this study, questionnaires were used to collect the data from the respondents. Following procedures and techniques were implemented to conduct this proposed study. The population consisted of 5024 teachers from 297 secondary schools in the public sector in Mardan Division of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (According to Education Management Information System, 2016-17). Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is a province of Pakistan, there are seven divisions and thirty-five districts in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Mardan division is one of the divisions of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. There are two districts in Mardan division, district Mardan and district Swabi. The researcher have selected Mardan division for research study (Wikipedia, 2020). There were two hundred and ninety-seven (297) secondary schools in Mardan division, 96 schools were randomly selected for the study in public sector. The proportion of boys and girls schools from urban and rural areas was equal. The Nine hundred and sixty (960) teachers (480 teachers from District Mardan and 480 teachers from District Swabi) of urban and rural areas were randomly selected from 96 secondary schools. The ten teachers from each selected school ($10 \times 96 = 960$) were randomly selected.

Data Collection

The data was collected from the respondents through questionnaires. The researcher visited the sample schools personally to get the relevant information through the use of selected instruments. i.e. questionnaires. The teachers were instructed about the method of questionnaire filling. The respondents (teachers) were asked to mark on the suitable place one of the five categories ranging from "very negative effect to high effect" carrying the score 5 to 1 correspondingly, and also requested on another suitable place one of the three categories ranging from excellent to not satisfactory or other given options, carrying the score from 3 to 1

Data Analysis

The coded data was tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted category wise as teachers by utilizing descriptive and inferential statistical techniques such as frequency, Percentage, and ANOVA-Post-Hoc to get the true picture of the prevailing parameters affecting quality education among the public secondary schools of the District Mardan and Swabi and also analyzed by using SPSS.

Results And Interpretation

Table: 1: Opinions of teachers on principals' administrative authority related parameters affecting quality education

Sr. no.	Aspects	Level in schools			Comparison Group	Comparative effectiveness Mean (i-j)	F	P values
		Often (Oft)	Sometimes (SmT)	Never (Nv)				
1	Teachers prefer corporal punishment for their students.	60 (6%)	547 (57%)	353 (37%)	Oft&SmT Oft&Nv SmT&Nv (F=P<0.05)	-.52* .93* 1.46*	133.85	.00
2	Teachers prefer to maintain the discipline of the students.	655 (68%)	243 (25%)	62 (7%)	Oft&SmT Oft&Nv SmT&Nv (F=P<0.05)	.81* 1.82* 1.82*	202.26	.00

3	Teachers care about the uniform of the students.	721 (75%)	208 (22%)	31 (3%)	Oft&SmT Oft&Nv SmT&Nv (F=P<0.05)	.89* 2.73* 1.83*	339.20	.00
4	Teachers help the slow learner in academic affairs	531 (55%)	364 (38%)	65 (07%)	Oft&SmT Oft&Nv SmT&Nv (F=P<0.05)	.62* 3.05* 2.42*	664.73	.00
5.	Students obey teachers' orders in school matters.	617 (64%)	291 (30%)	52 (06%)	Oft&SmT Oft&Nv SmT&Nv (F=P<0.05)	1.18* 2.26* 1.07*	306.98	.00
6.	Teachers help in solving administrative problems for the principal.	502 (52%)	377 (39%)	81 (09%)	Oft&SmT Oft&Nv SmT&Nv (F=P<0.05)	-1.53* -1.19* .34	195.73	.00
7.	There is a cordial relationship between the principal and teachers.	623 (65%)	301 (31%)	36 (4%)	Oft&SmT Oft&Nv SmT&Nv (F=P<0.05)	.98* 2.47* 1.49*	307.69	.00
8.	There is a cordial relationship between teachers and students.	628 (66%)	290 (30%)	42 (4%)	Oft&SmT Oft&Nv SmT&Nv (F=P<0.05)	.82* 2.52* 1.70*	389.64	.00

*significant at the 0.05 level

Table 1 shows, the effect of principals' administrative authority-related parameters on quality education. For the first statement, the statistical values show that 57% of schools had teachers who preferred corporal punishment with a level of "sometimes", 37% prefer with "never", and 06% with "often", level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools where teachers preferred corporal punishment having a level of "sometimes", were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with "often", and "never", levels. Similarly, the schools with teachers having a level of "often", were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with "never", levels ($i-j=1.46$, $P<0.05$).

For 2nd statement, showing teachers prefer to maintain the discipline of students, the statistical values show that 68% of schools had teachers who preferred to maintain the discipline having the level of "often", 25% with "sometimes", and 07% with "never", level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools where teachers preferred to maintain the discipline of students having the level of "often", were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with a level of "sometimes", and "never". Similarly, the schools with teachers having the level of "sometimes", were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with "never", levels ($i-j=1.82$, $P<0.05$).

For the 3rd statement, showing teachers care about the uniform of the students, the statistical values show that 75% of schools had teachers who cared about the uniform of the students with the level of "often", 22% with "sometimes", and 03% with "never", level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools where teachers cared about the uniform of the students having the level of "often", were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with "sometimes" and "never". Similarly, the schools with teachers having a level of "sometimes", were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with "never" levels ($i-j=1.83$, $P<0.5$).

For the 4th statement, showing teachers help the slow learners in academic affairs, the statistical values show that 55% of schools had teachers who helped the slow learners with a level of "often", 38% with "sometimes", and 07% with "never", in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools where teachers helped the slow learners with the level of "often", were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with "sometimes", and "never". Similarly, the schools with teachers having a level of "sometimes", were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with "never", levels ($i-j=2.42$, $P<0.05$).

For the fifth statement, showing students obey teachers' order in school matters, the statistical values show that 64% of schools had students who obeyed teachers' order in school matters with the level of "often", 30% with "sometimes", and 06% with "never", in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools where students obeyed teachers' order in school matter having the level of "often", were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with a level of "sometimes", and "never". Similarly, the schools where students obeyed teachers' orders in school matters, having a level of "sometimes",

were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “never”, level (i-j= 1.07, P<0.05).

For the 6th statement, showing teachers help in solving administrative problems for principal, the statistical values show that 52% of schools had teachers who helped in solving administrative problems for a principal with the level of “often”, 39% with “sometimes”, and 09% with “never”, in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools having a level of “often”, were significantly (P<0.05) contributing in educational quality than the schools with “sometimes”, and “never”, levels. Similarly, the schools with teachers' help in solving problems for principals having a level of “sometimes”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with a level of “never” (i-j=-1.53, P<0.05).

For the seventh statement, showing the cordial relationship between principal and teachers, the statistical values show that 65% of schools had teachers who had cordial relationships with the level of “often”, 31% “sometimes”, and 04% with “never”, in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools where teachers had a cordial relationship with the principal with the level of “often”, were significantly (P<0.05) contributing to educational quality than the schools with “sometimes”, and “never”. Similarly, the schools having teachers who had a cordial relationship with the principal with a level of “sometimes”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “never” (i-j=1.49, P<0.05).

For the eighth statement, showing the cordial relationship between teachers and students, the statistical values show that 66% of schools had a cordial relationship between teachers and students, with a level of “often”, 30% with “sometimes”, and 04% with “never”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools with the cordial relationship between teachers and students with the level of “often”, were significantly (P<0.05) contributing in educational quality than the schools with the level of “sometimes” and “never” level. Similarly, the schools with the cordial relationship having a level of “sometimes”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “never” (i-j=1.70, P<0.05).

Table 2: Opinions of teachers about student-teacher ratio related parameters affecting quality education

Sr. no.	Aspects	Level in schools			Comparison Group	Comparative effectiveness Mean (i-j)	F	P values
		Fairly Adequate (FA)	Adequate (A)	Not Adequate (NA)				
1	Standard class size (30-35).	192 (20%)	381 (40%)	387 (40%)	F A&A F A &NA A &N A (F= P<0.05)	.84* 3.55* 2.71*	2.57	.00
2	The number of science teachers in school.	308 (32%)	498 (52%)	154 (16%)	F A&A F A&N A. A&NA (F=P<0.05)	.80* 3.15* 2.34*	1.09	.00
3	The number of arts teachers in school.	343 (36%)	547 (57%)	70 (7%)	F A&A F A&N A. A&N A (F=P<0.05)	.75* 2.91* 2.16*	573.6	.00
4	The overall number of teachers in school.	345 (36%)	469 (49%)	146 (15%)	F A&A F A&N A A&N A (F=P<0.05)	.74* 2.94* 2.19*	1886.5	.00
5.	Students- teachers' ratio in school.	260 (27%)	471 (49%)	229 (24%)	FA&A FA&N A A&N A (F=P<0.05)	.75* 2.97* 2.22*	928.2	.00

*Significant at 0.05 level

Table 2 indicates the effect of student-teacher ratio-related parameters on quality education. For the first statement, standard class size (30-35), the statistical values show that 40% of schools had standard class size with a level of “adequate”, 40% with “not adequate”, and 20% with “fairly adequate”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools with standard class size having a level of “adequate”, were significantly (P<0.05) contributing in educational quality than the schools with a level of “fairly adequate”, and “not adequate”. Similarly, the schools with standard class sizes having a level of “fairly adequate”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “not adequate” (i-j=2.71, P<0.05).

For the 2nd statement, showing the number of science teachers in school, the statistical values show that 52% of schools had many science teachers with a level of “adequate”, 32% with “fairly adequate”, and 16% with “not adequate”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools having the number of science teachers with a level of “adequate” were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with a level of “fairly adequate”, and “not adequate”. Similarly, the schools with science subject teachers having a level of “fairly adequate”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “not adequate” levels ($i-j=2.34, P<0.05$).

For the 3rd statement, showing the number of arts teachers in school, the statistical values show that 57% of schools had art teachers with a level of “adequate”, 36% with “fairly adequate”, and 07% with “not adequate”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools having art teachers with the level of “adequate”, were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with a level of “fairly adequate”, and “not adequate”. Similarly, the schools having the number of art teachers with a level of “fairly adequate”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “not adequate” ($i-j=2.16, P<0.05$).

For the 4th statement, showing the overall number of teachers in school, the statistical values show that 49% of schools had an overall number of teachers with a level of “adequate”, 36% with “fairly adequate”, and 15% with “not adequate”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools with the overall number of teachers having the level of “adequate”, were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with a level of “fairly adequate”, and “not adequate”. Similarly, the schools with the overall number of teachers having a level of “adequate”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “not adequate” ($i-j=2.19, P<0.05$).

For the 5th statement, showing proper student-teacher ratio, the statistical values show that 49% of schools had proper student-teacher ratio with a level of “fairly adequate”, 27% with “fairly adequate”, and 24% with “not adequate” level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools with proper student-teacher ratios having the level of “adequate”, were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with a level of “fairly adequate”, and “not adequate”. Similarly, the schools with a proper student-teacher ratio having a level of “fairly adequate” were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with a “not adequate” level ($i-j=2.22, P<0.05$).

Discussion

The following discussion was made based on the findings of the study:

Teachers punish their students physically to keep discipline in the class. It is also a fact that our learning environment declares that teachers are the best, whose class control is best, which is against the pedagogy of child centered approach are the significant parameters of quality education. When the teachers care about the uniform of the students and help the slow learner in academic affairs then the students will give good output in their results are the significant of quality education. When the students obey teachers’ order in school matters, and teachers help in solving administrative problems for the principal, and there is cordial relationship between the principal and teachers and as well as teachers and students are the significant parameters of quality education. It was also found that standard class size (30-35), the number of science, arts, and overall teachers and as well as student-teacher ratio in school in a balance ratio are the significant parameters of quality education.

The Way Forward

In the light of this study, the following recommendations are made based on findings and conclusions:

1. The government in all educational institutions has banned corporal punishment recently. The dominant slogan is “Don’t teach by punishment but teach by love”. In this situation, most of the teachers disliked it, especially in the public sector secondary schools. Therefore, the Government is suggested to allow the punishment for the students up to a proper limit to maintain discipline and care about the uniform so it will make sure the quality of education.
2. The Government is suggested that the principals of the schools may ensure their teachers help the slow learner in academic affairs, the teachers help in solving administrative problems for the principal, and as well as the students must obey teachers’ orders in the school problems so it can ensure the quality education.
3. The researcher suggests to the government that it will be the responsibility of the principals that he/she must create a conducive environment that there will be a cordial relationship between the principal and teachers and as well as between the teachers and students.
4. The Government is suggested that the students- teachers’ ratio will be on an equal basis of strength of students because if there is over-strength in the classes then it is difficult for the teachers to control. The teachers may not be able to check their homework and as well as to teach them easily. The standard class size may be up to 30-35.

5. The researcher suggests to the government that the science subject teachers, art subject teachers, and as well as the overall number of teachers in the school may be appointed based on the student-teacher ratio so it can ensure quality education.

References

- Berry, M. (2002). Healthy school environment and enhanced educational performance: The Case of Charles Young Elementary School. Washington, DC: USA.
- Crowther, F. (2000). Leadership for successful school revitalization: Lessons from recent Australian research. Paper presented at the annual meeting of AERA. New Orleans: LA.
- Education Management Information System, (2016-17). Government of KPK, Elementary & Secondary Education Department retrieved on 25th August 2014. <http://www.kpese.gov.pk/home/view.cfm?MenuID 1>
- Education System in Pakistan Problems. Issues & Solutions, pgc.edu. 17 November 2017. retrieved 24 March 2018.
- Fullan, M. (2001). Leading in a culture of change. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Gronn, P., & Hamilton, A. (2004). A bit more life in the leadership: Co-principal Ship as a distributed leadership practice. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 3(1), 35.
- Jacobson, S. (2011). Leadership affects student achievement and sustained school success. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 25 (1), 33-44.
- Kathleen, D. (2003). A Qualitative Study of Parameters that Influence the Decisions Regarding Assessment of Students' Competence in Practice Caledonian Nursing and Midwifery Research Centre, 98.
- Ministry of Education. (2008). Continuous Professional Development for School Teachers (A Guide Line). Addis Ababa; MoE.
- National Assessment and Accreditation Council (2007). Quality indicators for teacher education. Bangalore: Commonwealth of Learning.
- Pakistan Bureau of Statistic, (2017). Enumeration of the Pakistani population, 15th March 2017 to 25th May 2017 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Districts_of_Khyber_Pakhtunkhwa
- Silns, H., & Mulford, B. (2002). Leadership and school results: Second international handbook of educational leadership and administration. Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Press.
- Spillane, J. (2007). Taking a distributed perspective to the school principals' workday. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 1 (6), 103-125.
- Wang, J. (2013). Web-age information management 14th International Conference, WAIM 2013, Beidaihe, China, June 14-16, 2013: proceedings. Berlin: Springer.

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